

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D7.6

Establishment of a raw material spectral knowledge base (alpha
version)

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Table of Content

Table of Content	3
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Deliverable Description	7
1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable	7
1.3 Intended Audience	7
1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables	8
2. Partner Responsibilities and Interdependencies	9
2.1 Overview	9
2.2 Roles by Work Package	9
2.3 Coordination Highlights / Next Steps	10
3. Technical Setup and Data Acquisition	11
3.1 Overview of Data Acquisition Campaigns	11
3.2 Airborne Hyperspectral Survey (DIMAP)	11
3.3 Ground Sampling and Laboratory Spectral Scanning (ICCS)	11
3.4 Satellite Observations (PRISMA)	11
3.5 Summary of Available Inputs	12
4. Data Integration Challenges and Observations	13
4.1 Sensor-Specific Characteristics	13
4.2 Field Spectral References (ASD)	13
4.3 Chemical Labeling and Validation Dataset	13
4.4 Interoperability and Format Standardization	13
5. Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB): Structure and Implementation	15
5.1 Purpose and Scope	15
5.2 CoreSmart Input Specification	15
5.3 RMSKB Data Structure and Processing Workflow	15
5.4 CoreSmart Model Variants and Status	16
5.5 CoreSmart Functional Workflow in TerraFusion	16
5.6 Planned Extensions	17
6. Conclusions and Recommendation	18
6.1 Summary of Achievements	18
6.2 Outlook / Next Steps	18
7. Annexes	19
7.1 Annex 1	19

List of Tables

Table 1: Available input data from different sources..... 12

Table 2: CoreSmart module status and related input data 16

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
ASD	Analytical Spectral Devices (field spectroradiometer)
ATCOR-4	Atmospheric and Topographic Correction software (version 4)
EO	Earth Observation
ENMAP	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (hyperspectral satellite mission)
ENVI	Environment for Visualizing Images (geospatial analysis software)
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDF5 / .he5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (PRISMA scene file structure)
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
L2D	Level 2D product (PRISMA atmospheric corrected data)
PRISMA	PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (Italian hyperspectral satellite)
REST	Representational State Transfer (web service API standard)
RMSKB	Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base
SPECIM	Spectral Imaging Ltd. (lab SWIR spectrometer manufacturer)
SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared
VNIR	Visible and Near-Infrared

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the initial establishment of a scalable Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB), focusing on hyperspectral analysis from VNIR to SWIR (~1000–2450 nm) across laboratory, airborne, and satellite platforms. Coordinated by GEOS under Task 7.4, the RMSKB forms a technical cornerstone of the TERRAVISION platform and provides harmonized inputs for AI-driven mineral content prediction using the CoreSmart module. Activities included airborne acquisition over two demonstrator sites, surface sampling, lab-based SWIR spectral scanning, and ingestion of satellite data (PRISMA). Foundational components have been completed, and the alignment of workflows across Work Packages in the next Project phase will further enhance system integration.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this deliverable are:

- To deploy a modern hyperspectral acquisition setup over TERRAVISION demonstrator sites
- To establish a harmonized spectral knowledge base supporting CoreSmart application across multiple platforms
- To initiate the platform integration of CoreSmart for SWIR-based metal prediction services within TerraFusion

Status: Achieved to a significant degree. Airborne campaigns and lab scanning were completed. Harmonization pipelines and platform integration are progressing with ITA and CORE IC.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

Airborne Campaign:

DIMAP conducted VNIR/SWIR hyperspectral flights in September 2024 over Tharsis and Canteras using HySpex sensors. Data were processed to reflectance using ATCOR-4 with scene-specific atmospheric parameters. VNIR-SWIR transition and detector jump issues were addressed through tailored correction procedures. Details regarding the airborne data collection campaign and subsequent data pre-processing and QC can be found in Deliverable 5.2.

Lab Sampling:

ICCS scanned 500+ rock samples using SPECIM SWIR instrumentation.

Satellite Data:

PRISMA .he5 L2D scenes were acquired and processed. VNIR and SWIR cubes require alignment through stitching, resampling, and co-registration.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

RMSKB v1 has been established with a focus on the SWIR spectral region (1000–2450 nm), standardized to 4 nm band spacing for compatibility across all input platforms. This structure allows integration of airborne, lab, and satellite data into a unified spectral domain suitable

for prediction. CoreSmart has been implemented as a backend module within the TerraFusion platform and is operational for Fe and Cu prediction. Internally, CoreSmart maintains separate trained pipelines for each element, and users can select specific metals or request full-spectrum predictions. API workflows, metadata requirements, and REST-based integration services are in active development with CORE IC.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- RMSKB v1 initiated with lab, airborne, and satellite SWIR data
- DIMAP provided processed airborne data; ICCS conducted lab scanning
- Tharsis and Canteras data analyzed
- CoreSmart v1 supports Fe and Cu predictions; future expansion to additional elements planned
- TerraFusion GUI and upload/processing pipelines are under design
- Harmonization tasks led by ITA are advancing ARD readiness and model scalability
- Final data basis for comprehensive CoreSmart module training/testing expected by Q4 2025

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable (D7.6A) presents the first version of the Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB), developed under Task 7.4 of the TERRAVISION project. The RMSKB is a central component of TERRAVISION’s Earth Observation (EO)-based exploration services, integrating hyperspectral datasets from laboratory, airborne, and satellite sources across multiple demonstrator mining sites. This alpha version of the knowledge base focuses on establishing processing pipelines, standardizing spectral input data, and initiating the integration of predictive tools (such as CoreSmart) for mineral content prediction. The deliverable also captures interdependencies with data acquisition (WP5), pre-processing and harmonization (WP7, led by ITA), and validation tasks in subsequent work packages (notably WP9).

In addition to its role in harmonizing spectral inputs, the RMSKB underpins predictive analytics services within the TERRAVISION platform architecture. As described in D4.4, CoreSmart—developed and operated by GEOS—will be integrated into the TerraFusion platform as a backend service module. RMSKB content will directly support model inputs, validation processes, and user-facing functionalities such as remote prediction interfaces, reinforcing Task 7.4’s strategic role as a technical and architectural enabler.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the setup, early population, and technical challenges associated with creating a scalable and harmonized spectral knowledge base focused on hyperspectral (VNIR/SWIR) data. It captures the results of airborne campaigns, lab-based spectral acquisitions, and sample metadata collection conducted in the first 18 months of the project. As outlined in the Grant Agreement, D7.6A represents the alpha stage of this data integration effort, serving as a preparatory step toward later, fully validated implementations.

Beyond data integration, this deliverable also provides the functional foundations for predictive services in the TerraFusion platform. GEOS is responsible for providing CoreSmart model logic, API specifications, and compatibility rules to platform developers. These interfaces will allow CoreSmart to interact with user uploads, run predictions across lab, airborne, or satellite data inputs, and return structured outputs, thus enabling real-time EO-based mineral analysis.

1.3 Intended Audience

As the Dissemination level of D7.6 is public, this document is intended for a wide audience ranging from:

- Consortium partners involved in spectral data processing, integration, and modeling (GEOS, ICCS, DIMAP, ITA)

- Leaders of downstream tasks that depend on the RMSKB, particularly WP9 (Raw Material Exploration)
- Technical leads for spectral harmonization and TerraFusion platform integration (CORE IC, ICCS)
- Project managers and reviewers monitoring progress against the TERRAVISION Grant Agreement
- External stakeholders interested in EO data standardization, AI-based prediction, and mineral exploration workflows

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable is structured to provide both a progress update and a technical foundation for further development of hyperspectral services under TERRAVISION. It includes the following sections:

- **Section 1: Introduction** – Context, purpose, and audience for the deliverable
- **Section 2: Partner Responsibilities and Interdependencies** – Roles and coordination among WP5, WP7, WP9
- **Section 3: Technical Setup and Data Acquisition** – Campaign details, sensors, and data streams
- **Section 4: Data Integration Challenges and Observations** – Issues with sensor harmonization, missing references, and data gaps
- **Section 5: Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB): Structure and Implementation** – Database structure, ingestion workflows, CoreSmart model strategy, and TerraFusion integration

This deliverable is closely related to the following work packages:

- **WP5 (Data Acquisition):** Airborne data provision by DIMAP
- **WP7 (ARD and Spectral Processing):** Data harmonization and format compatibility led by ITA
- **WP9 (Sampling and Validation Services):** Provision of field and lab validation data by ICCS
- **WP4 (Platform Architecture):** Design and implementation of backend modules and interfaces; requires GEOS contributions to CoreSmart logic and API endpoints

2. Partner Responsibilities and Interdependencies

2.1 Overview

Task 7.4 sits at the intersection of data acquisition (WP5), data processing and harmonization (WP7), platform integration (WP4), and downstream EO-based service development (WP9 and WP10). Its successful execution relies on coordinated planning between several TERRAVISION partners contributing expertise in airborne sensing, lab-based spectroscopy, ARD production, platform design, and predictive modelling. GEOS, as task leader, collaborates closely with ITA, ICCS, DIMAP, and CORE IC to ensure that hyperspectral data from multiple sources can be integrated and structured within the Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB), and that this resource supports AI-driven service functionality within the TerraFusion environment.

2.2 Roles by Work Package

WP5 – Large EO Data Ecosystem (Data Acquisition)

Lead: SINTEF; DIMAP (Task 5.2)

- Execution of airborne hyperspectral campaigns (VNIR/SWIR) over TV demonstrators
- Technical responsibility for ground-based ASD measurements for data calibration
- Delivery of radiometrically and geometrically corrected data and relevant metadata and processing reports

WP7 – ARD Data and Spectral Signatures (Data Processing and Harmonization)

Lead: ITA (ARD); GEOS (Task 7.4)

- GEOS is responsible for the RMSKB setup, spectral ingestion workflows, and CoreSmart model adaptation.
- ITA leads the development of the ARD processing framework, including atmospheric correction, spectral resampling, and metadata standardization.
- DIMAP supports the integration by providing calibration documentation and sensor specifications.
- ICCS contributes spectral lab data from scanned rock samples.

WP9 – Raw Material Exploration (Sampling and Validation)

Lead: ICCS; GEOS, VITO (Task 9.1, 9.4)

- Conducted surface rock sampling and organized laboratory spectral scanning using SWIR instrumentation
- Coordinated chemical assays of samples
- Provides reference datasets intended for validation of model performance

Dependencies:

- Ground sampling followed the airborne survey, which limited direct temporal alignment for calibration
- Coordination challenges contributed to the absence of contemporaneous field spectral references

WP4 – Platform Architecture and Integration

Leads: ICCS, CORE IC

- Responsible for implementing the TerraFusion platform backend and frontend services
- Defines interfaces for service modules like CoreSmart

Dependencies:

- GEOS must deliver CoreSmart API logic, prediction input requirements, and data format standards to allow seamless platform integration
- Coordination is required between GEOS and CORE IC to define user-facing functionality, spectral upload workflows, and result formatting in alignment with UI expectations outlined in D4.4

2.3 Coordination Highlights / Next Steps

The project work packages have been aligned to support efficient data flow and integration. Task 7.4 has coordinated with WP5, WP7, WP9, and WP4 to facilitate data provision, processing, and model implementation. As workflows mature, cross-WP communication and integration will continue to strengthen the TERRAVISION infrastructure.

- Align future airborne and ground campaigns through shared milestones
- Maintain proactive communication between technical, validation, and integration teams
- Streamline metadata handover and ensure harmonized interfaces for platform components

3. Technical Setup and Data Acquisition

3.1 Overview of Data Acquisition Campaigns

Task 7.4 activities focused on collecting and preparing hyperspectral datasets to serve as input for the Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB). This involved airborne imaging, laboratory spectral scanning, and the acquisition of satellite-based observations. The primary target sites were Tharsis and Canteras. Data were collected across platforms (airborne, lab, satellite).

3.2 Airborne Hyperspectral Survey (DIMAP)

DIMAP conducted airborne campaigns in September 2024 over Tharsis and Canteras using a dual HySpex system:

- **VNIR (Neo HySpex 1600):** 400–1000 nm, 160 bands, ~1.2 m GSD
- **SWIR (Neo HySpex 320e):** 1000–2500 nm, 256 bands, ~2.5 m GSD

Aircraft flights followed pre-programmed patterns, covering more than 330 km² over Tharsis and ~10 km² at Canteras. Data were radiometrically calibrated and georectified using HySpex RAD/NAV, PARGE, and ATCOR-4. The processing pipeline included boresight correction, scan angle application, and reflectance retrieval using the ATCOR-4f flat-terrain model. Atmospheric parameters (e.g., water vapor) were estimated per scene.

3.3 Ground Sampling and Laboratory Spectral Scanning (ICCS)

Following airborne acquisitions, rock samples were collected from both sites:

- **Tharsis:** ~420 samples
- **Canteras:** ~96 samples

Samples were scanned at ICCS using a SPECIM SWIR lab hyperspectral setup (1000–2500 nm). The data were pre-processed to extract clean SWIR spectral signatures for later use in validation and exploratory analysis. Chemical assay data are available for Canteras.

3.4 Satellite Observations (PRISMA)

Archived PRISMA L2D scenes (delivered as .he5 files) were downloaded for Canteras and Tharsis' sites. Each file contains:

- Separate VNIR and SWIR cubes
- Geolocation fields (lat/lon)
- Metadata for band centres and pixel error matrices

VNIR and SWIR regions are not natively harmonized and require spectral stitching, band exclusion, and resampling. Because of detector discontinuities and spectral gaps (~0.98 μm), PRISMA data will initially be limited to SWIR-only application in CoreSmart-SAT.

3.5 Summary of Available Inputs

Source	Type	Platform	Status
DIMAP	Airborne VNIR/SWIR	HySpex system	Acquired; ATCOR-processed reflectance
ICCS	Lab SWIR	SPECIM	Acquired; Canteras assays complete
PRISMA	Satellite VNIR/SWIR	.he5 format	Downloaded; pre-processing planned (ITA)
DIMAP (ASD)	Field reference	TerraSpec 4	To be acquired in Q3 2025

Table 1: Available input data from different sources.

This configuration defines the first version of the RMSKB. It is focused on SWIR-only harmonization to accommodate data quality limitations and VNIR-SWIR harmonisation challenges across all platforms. Future updates may expand this scope depending on validation results and ARD developments.

4. Data Integration Challenges and Observations

This section highlights the integration approaches and harmonization strategies for the datasets gathered. Sensor-specific characteristics were addressed using appropriate resampling and normalization procedures, and laboratory measurements contribute high-resolution inputs for validation and modeling. All platforms are being integrated into a unified ARD framework.

4.1 Sensor-Specific Characteristics

Each acquisition platform used in Task 7.4 presents specific sensor characteristics. The airborne campaign delivered high-quality VNIR and SWIR imagery via the Neo HySpex system, which are harmonized through interpolation, reflectance correction, and co-registration techniques. Adjustments to spatial resolution and band alignment ensure consistency across airborne, lab, and satellite inputs.

In the case of satellite data, PRISMA further complicates alignment. The .he5 files contain separate VNIR and SWIR cubes, which are not natively harmonized. Merging these data cubes requires substantial resampling, offset correction, and atmospheric calibration.

Laboratory spectra (SPECIM SWIR) provide higher consistency due to controlled lighting and measurement conditions. However, lab data lacks contextual spatial variability, which complicates training of models meant for airborne/satellite application.

4.2 Field Spectral References (ASD)

The TerraSpec 4 Hi-Res spectroradiometer is designated to support the airborne campaign by providing ground-based reference reflectance data. Such data will be included in upcoming campaigns to enhance spectral correction and alignment protocols. Planning is underway to ensure comprehensive acquisition strategies across future datasets.

4.3 Chemical Labeling and Validation Dataset

Over 500 surface rock samples were collected and scanned spectrally. Lab assays have been integrated where available, supporting validation workflows. Additional datasets are expected to further enrich CoreSmart training and evaluation.

4.4 Interoperability and Format Standardization

VNIR/SWIR datasets arrive in various formats and structures:

- DIMAP airborne data: ENVI-compatible reflectance cubes with ATCOR-4 correction.
- ICCS lab data: Processed SWIR cubes with associated sample IDs and assay metadata.
- PRISMA satellite scenes: Delivered as .he5 files requiring conversion, stitching, and alignment.

ITA is developing a unified ARD framework, including spectral resampling, band rejection, metadata normalization, and standardized storage formats for ingestion into the RMSKB.

5. Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB): Structure and Implementation

5.1 Purpose and Scope

The Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB) provides the harmonized spectral foundation for CoreSmart predictions across TERRAVISION's lab, airborne, and satellite data sources. Its role is twofold: (1) to standardize hyperspectral inputs from heterogeneous sensors and (2) to ensure compatibility with the AI-driven CoreSmart prediction modules deployed on the TerraFusion platform. Given the diversity of input systems, RMSKB must support data normalization, interpolation, metadata traceability, and input validation protocols for consistent model execution.

5.2 CoreSmart Input Specification

To maintain interoperability across platforms, all spectral inputs to CoreSmart are:

- **Restricted to the SWIR range: 1000–2450 nm**, where all platforms have the highest overlap and data quality
- **Interpolated to a fixed 4 nm band spacing**, resulting in approximately 363 input features
- **Normalized** via continuum removal and mean-scaling to match the statistical profile of the HyLogger training set
- **Clipped** to exclude known atmospheric absorption regions (e.g., ~1400 nm, ~1900 nm)

This approach ensures spectral comparability regardless of source origin and aligns with the spectral resolution of the legacy HyLogger3 training dataset used by CoreSmart.

5.3 RMSKB Data Structure and Processing Workflow

The RMSKB is structured as a modular database indexed by:

- Site and acquisition platform (Lab, Airborne, Satellite)
- Spectral metadata (sensor ID, resolution, range)
- Processing history (corrections applied, reference libraries used)
- Label availability (e.g. chemical assays)

The ingestion pipeline includes:

1. **Format conversion** from ENVI, HDF5 (.he5), or raw sensor-specific formats
2. **Spectral interpolation** to 4 nm spacing over 1000–2450 nm

3. **Band exclusion** and water absorption masking
4. **Continuum removal and normalization**
5. **Metadata tagging** for traceability and model version control

5.4 CoreSmart Model Variants and Status

Variant	Source	Status	Notes
CoreSmart-LAB	ICCS lab scans	In development	Assay-labelled; model testable only (not trainable)
CoreSmart-AIR	DIMAP HySpex	In design	Requires ARD harmonization and Tharsis assay data
CoreSmart-SAT	PRISMA (.he5)	In planning	Awaiting geometric correction and band alignment

Table 2: CoreSmart module status and related input data.

All models share the same input format and pre-processing logic but differ in spatial resolution, noise sensitivity, and output interpretation. Internally, each CoreSmart model maintains a dedicated machine learning pipeline per target element (e.g., Fe, Cu, Zn, Pb). These pipelines are trained separately and accessed conditionally based on user input.

5.5 CoreSmart Functional Workflow in TerraFusion

The CoreSmart module is deployed as a containerized background process within the **Linux-based TerraFusion platform**. It is accessed via the user interface, following this sequence:

1. **User Upload:**
 - Spectral file (lab, airborne, or satellite) uploaded via GUI
2. **Compatibility Check:**
 - File type, wavelength range, and resolution verified
 - If needed, the input is forwarded to a pre-processing module
3. **Pre-processing:**
 - Interpolation to 4 nm SWIR grid
 - Continuum removal
 - Optional masking of water absorption bands
4. **Model Selection:**
 - User chooses platform-specific model (LAB, AIR, SAT)

- User either selects individual metal(s) of interest (e.g., Fe, Cu) or runs full prediction

5. Prediction Execution:

- Spectra passed to corresponding internal models for each element
- Predictions generated per target element

6. Output Packaging:

- Predictions linked to sample ID or pixel coordinates
- Delivered as downloadable CSV, TXT, or GeoTIFF (for maps)
- Optional: Output piped into downstream modules (e.g. WP9 services)

Currently, a working prototype is available for **Fe and Cu prediction**. This module will be made available as an appendix (including a download link). Future versions are expected to expand functionality to include additional elements such as **Au, Ag, Zn, Co, Pb**, and others, subject to data availability and model performance.

GEOS will provide API definitions, compatibility rules, and output formatting guidelines to CORE IC and ICCS for platform integration, as outlined in D4.4.

5.6 Planned Extensions

- Upgrade of CoreSmart to support full-cube (380–2500 nm) inputs in V2 (LAB only)
- Integration of EnMAP satellite sources if available, tasked
- UI refinements to support upload templates and auto-matching metadata
- Publication of spectral compatibility matrix and sample input specifications for users
- Addition of new elemental prediction pipelines as training data becomes available

The RMSKB and CoreSmart modules are thus both technical and architectural cornerstones of the TERRAVISION platform's predictive service infrastructure.

6. Conclusions and Recommendation

6.1 Summary of Achievements

This deliverable has successfully initiated the Raw Material Spectral Knowledge Base (RMSKB) and its integration into the broader TERRAVISION architecture. Major milestones include the completion of airborne and lab spectral data acquisition, the development of a standardized pre-processing workflow for SWIR data, and the deployment of CoreSmart v1 as a backend prediction module within the TerraFusion platform. The system currently supports Fe and Cu predictions and demonstrates the feasibility of scalable, harmonized EO-based mineral analytics. Integration across ARD, RMSKB, and prediction pipelines is still ongoing and dependent on metadata compatibility and QA/QC routines

6.2 Outlook / Next Steps

A third coordinated acquisition campaign is planned for 2025 at the Ternamag site, incorporating satellite, airborne, and field efforts. This will support the comprehensive validation of CoreSmart and broaden elemental prediction capabilities (e.g., Zn, Pb, Co, Au, Ag).

- Continue synchronized data acquisition strategies
- Include ground-based field data in future acquisition plans
- Enhance QA/QC frameworks for spectral data
- Foster active dialogue between data and platform developers for seamless integration

Task 7.4 and its outputs form the critical backbone for harmonized data ingestion and model-driven mineral prediction services. Continued coordination and iterative development are essential for realizing the full potential of the TERRAVISION platform.

7. Annexes

7.1 Annex 1

The Demo CoreSmart Module, compatible with Linux, is now available and has been shared between GEOS and ICCS to initiate its integration into the TERRAVISION platform.